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Effect of Social Networking Sites in Communication of Information in Distance Education : A Literature Review

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Abstract :

Social Networking Sites (SNS) are making people addictive because of their features like sharing and communication and has become part of daily life. These websites has made information to share in real time and communicate with learners and teachers in real time. In this paper, the author explores the effect of SNS in Sharing and Communication of information in Distance Education. SNS are used for entertaining and distracts learners from learning academic studies, but if used under proper supervision of teachers and if it is based on sound pedagogical principles it is very effective and useful in distance education where distance between teachers and learners are more and it takes much time for learners to communicate with their teachers and other learners.

Introduction :

Social Networking Sites (SNS) made possible to disseminate information not only at tremendous speed and to a larger distance but it also helped learners to share information, ideas, articulate their social network, and establish connections with their teachers and their colleagues, thus it helped educators to use SNS for enhancing teaching and learning and also for transferring text, images, audio, video to learners within a short period of time and to a larger distance. In recent years non formal education such as open schools or distance education has become more popular among learners because of its flexibility with respect to distance and time, similarly SNSs such as Facebook, Friendster, LinkedIn, LiveJournal, and MySpace are becoming popular and extensively used by large number of internet users for communication and sharing of information thus as observed by National School Boards Association [NSBA], it seems logical to merge these popular two technologies with the goal of improving online teaching and learning (Kevin ,et al.,2010).

George (2006) observed that, popular press coverage of SNSs has emphasized potential privacy concerns, primarily concerning the safety of younger users. As cited in (Boyd & Nicole, 2007) a study by Jagatic, Johnson, Jakobsson, and Menczer (2007) examine security issues and SNSs, they used freely accessible profile data from SNSs to craft a "phishing" scheme that appeared to originate from a friend on the network; their targets were much more likely to give away information to this "friend" than to a perceived stranger.

Objective :

- 1) Review the Effect of SNS in communication of information in distance education.
- 2) Study Effect of SNS in collaborating learning, through literature review.
- 3) Study Effect of SNS in sharing of information, through literature review.

expanded to other colleges. Facebook has met with some controversy being blocked in countries such as, China, Syria and Iran. The original concept for Facebook came from the colloquial name for books given out at the start of the academic year by universities designed to help students get to know one another better (Timeline: a history of SNS). To improve business networks a new wave of SNS began with launch of Ryze.com in 2001. As cited in (Boyd & Nicole, 2007), Scott A observe, that the Ryze's founder, first introduced the site to his friends—primarily members of the San Francisco business and technology community, including the entrepreneurs and investors behind many future SNSs. In 2011 Google a search engine giant introduced SNS Google Plus. The first thing users are introduced to is the Stream. It's much like the Facebook News Feed, allowing users to share photos, videos, links or their location with friends (Parr, 2011).

Effect of SNS in Communication of Information :

Web 2.0 technologies made possible for the learners to communicate, collaborate and share information 24 hours a day and 7 days in a week with creating, editing, tagging and rating content instantaneously, thus making interaction among learners in an exciting way, besides this learner can communicate with their teachers as well as co-learners synchronously as well as asynchronously. In their research (Yang & Tang, 2003, p.93) has found that the effect of SNS on students, in online education has a positive effect in performance and communication (friendly advising and adversarial) of teachers with their students. As cited in (Walsh, 2009, p. 27) Social networking sites such as Facebook and MySpace allow students in classes (face-to-face or online) and informal learners to create online communities. Although the sites are public,

Individuals or groups can choose to close off their space, limiting it to friends or classmates. SNS has turned the concept of "learning" on its head. It's no longer about waiting to be taught or trained, but about individuals having the power in their own hands to deal with their own learning problems much more quickly and efficiently than before (Social Media and its Impact on Work place learning). As cited in (Ellison, Stenfield, & Lampe, 2007), users of Facebook engage in "searching" for people with whom they have an offline connection more than they "browse" for complete strangers to meet.

As cited in (Social Media and its Impact on Work place learning) Marcia Conner and Tony Bingham reinforce the significance of social media in their recently published book, *The New Social Learning*, as "At its most basic level, new social learning can result in people becoming more informed, gaining a wider perspective, and being able to make better decisions by engaging with others. It acknowledges that learning happens with and through other people, as a matter of participating in a community, not just by acquiring knowledge. Most of what we learn at work and elsewhere comes from engaging in networks where people co-create, collaborate and share knowledge, fully participating and actively engaging, driving and guiding their learning through whatever topics will help them improve." Learners as collaborators and team players SNS are designed to support users working, thinking and acting together. They also require

listening and comprising skills. Learners may need to ask others for help and advice in using services, or understand how platforms work by observing others, particularly in complex gaming or virtual environments. Once users have developed confidence in a new environment, they will also have gained the experience to help others (Young People And Social Networking Services).

As cited in (Collaborative Learning in Social Networks), Evan Rosen describes in his book, *The Culture of Collaboration*, collaboration as a way of creating value within specified spaces, and introduces the Ten Cultural Elements of Collaboration: Trust, Sharing, Goals, Innovation, Environment, Collaborative Chaos, Constructive Confrontation, Communication, Community and Value. He purports that value creation is an integral part for collaboration. In their paper, (Yin, Tabata, & Ogata, 2009) propose a SNS based collaborative learning service in ubiquitous environment. It supports the learner to get help from the other SNS members, at the end makes them help each other. The service allowed the users use the service to search the person, who can solve the problem, and an appropriate request chain of friends (CF) will be advanced, upon their request, and then the learner contacts the helper for help tracing the CF. SNS have improve the collaborative learning process in distance education. It has helped collaborative learning flourish because of the benefit of online study groups, online printing for study guides and assignments, and international collaboration for different perspectives. These study groups are often held on sites such as Facebook and on instant messaging programs such as Skype, thus helping learners to study any subject in the comfort of their own home. Similarly learners can study any topic they wish to and debate their ideas with people all over the world (Social Networking And Collaborative Learning).

Findings :

From literature review it has been found that SNS increases performance of learner and helps in learning through communication, collaboration and sharing of information, thus Distance Education learners gets an opportunity to communicate and share information through features present in SNS. Web 2.0 technologies made possible for the learners to communicate, collaborate and share information 24 hours a day and 7 days in a week with creating, editing, tagging and rating content instantaneously, thus making interaction among learners in an exciting way. besides this learner can communicate with their teachers as well as co-learners synchronously as well as asynchronously. SNS such as Facebook, MySpace and LinkedIn helps learners in creating learning communities which enhances in sharing and collaboration of knowledge. In these sites applications and features are provided for security and safety of learners, so that learners are safe from the threats scammers and hackers. There other features which limits access of post to unknown users and limits accessibility to friends or known circles, best example of such SNS is GooglePlus. In acquiring knowledge and skills, most of what we learn at work and elsewhere comes from engaging in networks where people co-create, collaborate and share knowledge, fully participating and actively engaging and driving.

Conclusions :

Social Networking Sites are the most widely used websites among internet users for communicating, sharing and collaborating. These sites are popular, flexible, cheap and easy to use; similarly Distance Education system is also popular, flexible and cheap. Thus both help learners to acquire education and learning without any hassle and hence they are the most widely used popular among learners. In this review of research findings suggests that features in SNSs facilitates communication among learners and its features such as posts, messages and status made information available 24 hours in a day and 7 days in a week, for learners as well as teachers. There are other applications such as documents and pages which displays information to the learners so that they can access it asynchronously. Applications such text messaging and instant messaging also helps learners to share information synchronously in the real time and these applications are free to use. Sharing of information is possible in the SNS with applications such as share posts and subscriptions from different users and groups.

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